

Assessing the Difference Between Pure Black Coffee and Dark Chocolate Among CvSU-CCAT Second Year Bse-Science Students as Stimulants for Exam Preparation A.Y 2025-2026

Angeles, Loren kate D.¹, Bleza, Lhesly Anne M.², and Delicano Hyacinth Nicole M.³

¹Department of Teacher Education, Cavite State University CCAT Campus, Rosario, Cavite, Philippines

*Correspondence: lorenkate.angeles@cvsu.edu.ph ¹, lheslyanne.bleza@cvsu.edu.ph ², hyacinthnicole.delicano@cvsu.edu.ph ³

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to assess the differences between pure black coffee and dark chocolate as stimulants used during examinations and to determine which provides more effective cognitive support among second-year Science Education students. Specifically, the study examined how each stimulant influences students' alertness, focus, mental endurance, and perceived examination performance. A comparative quantitative research design was employed, using a structured and validated Likert-scale survey developed with guidance from faculty experts. The questionnaire was administered to 40 second-year Science Education students, with 20 regularly consuming pure black coffee and 20 consuming dark chocolate before examination periods. Participants' ages ranged from 18 to 21+, with 18 years old (2.5%), 19 years old (40%), 20 years old (22.5%), and 21+ years old (35%). Students came from Second Year Section A (62.5%) and Section B (37.5%), and the sample included their gender, 24 females (60%) and 16 males (40%).

The findings indicate that pure black coffee was generally perceived as more effective for alertness, with a mean perceived effectiveness of (M=28.50, SD=5.357) and scores ranging from 17 to 36, showing moderate variability in students' perceptions and overall higher perceived effectiveness in enhancing study performance and energy. In contrast, dark chocolate was perceived as more effective for focus and concentration, with a mean score of (M=40.85, SD=2.961) and scores ranging from 36 to 47, indicating relatively consistent perceptions among students. Overall, dark chocolate was perceived as a superior stimulant compared to pure black coffee, with a mean perceived effectiveness of (M=38.20, SD=3.548) and scores ranging from 30 to 47, suggesting it provided a consistently more effective stimulant effect during study sessions.

Keywords: *Pure black coffee, Dark chocolate, Perceived effectiveness, Cognitive performance, Alertness, Focus, Concentration, Second-year Science Education Students*

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1. Introduction

In the present time, students, particularly college students, face many responsibilities beyond their academic obligations. Managing tasks such as assignments, activities, Family obligations, and exam preparation often limits the time they have for effective studying. Academic assessments such as quizzes and exams play a vital role in determining overall performance, and students' success in these assessments significantly influences their academic standing (Skrbinjek, 2023). However, many students struggle to manage their study time due to procrastination, which may result from stress, anxiety, or personal habits commonly observed among learners. These challenges highlight the importance of finding strategies that help students maintain productivity, improve their academic performance, and maintain their well-being. As students move forward in their educational journey, they face different challenges and transitions that naturally bring stress. This may stem from academic demands, personal development, and the need to adapt to new environments all of which are integral parts of their learning experience (Iqra, 2024).

Previous studies have found that students often use stimulants to enhance alertness, concentration, and cognitive performance during periods of heavy academic workload. Caffeine, one of the most widely consumed stimulants worldwide, is particularly prevalent among students due to demanding schedules and academic pressure (Alqawasmi et al., 2024). Black coffee, a popular source of caffeine, is considered a nootropic that may enhance focus, mental alertness, and cognitive functioning, while also providing additional benefits such as supporting metabolism and supplying antioxidants (Shoemaker, 2021). These findings demonstrate that stimulant consumption is a common response to academic challenges, reflecting broader issues of stress, time management, and the need for effective study strategies.

Among commonly consumed stimulants, students often rely on dark chocolate or pure black coffee to support their cognitive performance during exam preparation. Dark chocolate contains cocoa flavanols, theobromine, and moderate caffeine, whereas black coffee provides higher caffeine levels, both of which can influence alertness, concentration, and working memory (Neglig, 2013). Despite their widespread use, the comparative effectiveness of these stimulants in supporting exam-related cognitive demands remains uncertain. This study aims to examine how each stimulant affects alertness, focus, memory, and overall cognitive functioning during exam-like tasks, and to identify the benefits of each without assuming that one is better than the other.

Improving students' academic performance and well-being is essential for effective exam preparation. This study highlights practical strategies that can help students manage their study time, reduce stress, and use stimulants such as dark chocolate and black coffee safely. Parents and educators play a key role in supporting these strategies by encouraging healthy study habits, providing guidance, and fostering awareness of safe stimulant consumption. Applying these approaches allows students to improve their concentration, learning efficiency, and overall mental sharpness without compromising their physical or mental health.

This study examines the differences between dark chocolate and pure black coffee on students' alertness, focus, memory, and overall cognitive performance, without assuming one is superior. The findings aim to guide students in making informed study and stimulant choices, while providing educators and parents with evidence-based insights to support effective, safe learning and promote both academic success and long-term well-being.

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2. Methodology

This study utilized a quasi-experimental research design to assess the difference between Pure Black Coffee and Dark Chocolate on students' cognitive performance during exam preparation. The design allowed for a systematic comparison of participants' perceived cognitive outcomes under two stimulant conditions, specifically in terms of alertness, focus, memory retention, and overall cognitive functioning.

The participants of the study consisted of 40 second-year Science Education students from sections A and B of Cavite State University–CCAT Campus, comprising 16 males and 24 females. All participants reported consuming caffeinated products, specifically 20 participants for Pure Black Coffee and 20 participants also for Dark Chocolate, as part of their study routine before examinations. Data were collected using a researcher-developed structured questionnaire employing a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Selected items were adapted from Alqawasmī et al. (2024), while the remaining items were developed by the researchers to measure students' perceived levels of alertness, focus, memory, and overall cognitive performance after consuming each stimulant.

The questionnaire was reviewed by a panel of experienced educators, including the Research Adviser and the Head Chairperson, to ensure content validity. After obtaining the necessary permissions from the Research Adviser and the Head Chairperson of Cavite State University–CCAT Campus, the questionnaires were distributed to the selected participants. Completed questionnaires were collected and prepared for data analysis. Data analysis was conducted using Descriptive and paired t-test tools. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores, were used to summarize participants' responses. To determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the perceived effectiveness of Pure Black Coffee and Dark Chocolate on cognitive performance, paired-sample t-tests were employed, focusing on differences in alertness, focus, memory retention, and overall examination readiness.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the conduct of the study. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed of the purpose of the research prior to answering the questionnaire. The confidentiality of all responses was ensured, and no personal identifying information was disclosed or misused. The data were collected and analyzed objectively, without manipulation, to ensure the credibility and accuracy of the findings. Through this methodological approach, the study establishes a systematic framework for comparing pure black coffee and dark chocolate as stimulants for examination preparation. By combining careful survey design, appropriate statistical analysis, and adherence to ethical standards, the research aims to provide meaningful insights that may guide students in choosing effective and healthier stimulants to support their academic performance.

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3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Consumption of Stimulants among Participants

The study began by examining the consumption of stimulants among the 40 second-year Science Education students from both Section A and Section B. Students consumed either pure black coffee or dark chocolate in a mixed manner across the sections. Out of the total respondents, 20 (50%) reported consuming pure black coffee, while the remaining 20 (50%) consumed dark chocolate. This shows that both stimulants are equally preferred by students during exam preparation, regardless of their section, sex, or age.

Table 1. Consumption of Stimulants among Second-Year Science Education Students

Type of Stimulant	Total Number of Participants who Consumed	Percentage
Pure Black Coffee	20	50%
Dark Chocolate	20	50%
TOTAL	40	100%

The sex distribution was further examined, revealing that 60% of the participants were female (24), and 40% were male (16). This distribution indicates that there were more female respondents than male respondents in the study. The difference in sex distribution is important as it may influence study habits, stimulant consumption, and perceptions of cognitive performance during examinations.

3.2 Demographic Profile of Participants

Table 2. Demographic Profile of Participants in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	24	60%
Male	16	40%
TOTAL	40	100%

The age distribution of the respondents was also analyzed to provide context for the findings of the study. The results revealed that 40% of the respondents were 19 years old, followed by 35% were 21+ years old, 22.5% were 20 years old, and 2.5% were 18 years old, with a total of 40 participants. This distribution indicates that the majority of respondents fall within the typical age range of second-year college students. Age is a relevant factor in this study, as cognitive stamina, caffeine tolerance, and study habits may vary depending on maturity and academic experience.

Table 3. Demographic Profile of Participants in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18	1	2.5%
19	16	40%
20	9	22.5%
21+	14	35%
TOTAL	40	100%

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The year and section distribution was examined, showing that 62.5% of the participants (n=25) were from Section A, while 37.5% (n=15) were from Section B. This distribution indicates that there were more respondents from Section A than Section B in the study. The section distribution provides contextual information about the composition of the respondents and is useful in understanding the representation of participants across the two sections.

Table 4. Demographic Profile of Participants in terms of Year and Section

Year and Section	Frequency	Percentage
2nd year-A	25	62.5%
2nd year- B	15	37.5
TOTAL	40	100%

3.3 Stimulant Consumption and Breakfast Intake of Respondents

The frequency of Pure Black Coffee consumption among the respondents was also analyzed. Out of the 20 respondents who reported consuming Pure Black Coffee, 60% (n =12) consumed it daily, 10% (n=2) consumed it 1–2 times per week, 5% (n = 1) consumed it 3–5 times per week, and 25% (n=5) reported rare consumption. This information is important as it provides context regarding the respondents' coffee consumption habits, which may be considered when interpreting their perceived levels of focus, concentration, and overall cognitive performance.

Table 5. How often do you consume Pure Black Coffee?

Times per Week	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	12	60%
1-2 times a week	2	10%
3-5 times a week	1	5%
Rarely	5	25%
Never	0	0
TOTAL	20	100%

The frequency of Dark chocolate consumption among the respondents was examined. Results showed that 35% (n=7) consumed dark chocolate daily, 25% (n=5) consumed it 1–2 times per week, 15% (n=3) consumed it 3–5 times per week, and 25% (n=5) consumed it rarely, while no respondents reported never consuming it. These consumption patterns provide context for interpreting respondents' perceptions of dark chocolate's effects on focus and concentration during exam preparation.

Table 6. How often do you consume Dark Chocolate?

Times per Week	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	7	35%
1-2 times a week	5	25%
3-5 times a week	3	15%
Rarely	5	25%
Never	0	0
TOTAL	20	100%

The study also investigated whether the participants ate breakfast before consuming the stimulants. Among the 40 respondents, 62.5% (n=25) reported that they ate breakfast, while 37.5% (n=15) reported that they did not. This result shows that a majority of the participants consumed breakfast prior to using stimulants during exam preparation.

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Table 7. Did you eat before consuming the stimulants?

Year and Section	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	25	62.5%
No	15	37.5%
TOTAL	40	100%

Overall, the respondents' stimulant consumption patterns and breakfast intake provide context for understanding their perceived alertness, focus, concentration, and cognitive performance during exam preparation.

3.4. Perceived Effectiveness (Objective 1)

In terms of the perceived effectiveness of stimulants, the results of the paired t-test revealed a statistically significant difference between pure black coffee and dark chocolate among second-year science students, $t(19) = 6.474, p < .001$. This indicates that students clearly perceive the two stimulants as differing in terms of their effectiveness in enhancing ability to complete study tasks, boosting energy to prepare better for exams, and contributing to improved academic and work performance.

Table 8. Paired Samples T-Test for perceived effectiveness

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p
COFFEE	CHOCOLATE	6.474	19	< .001

The findings showed that pure black coffee obtained a higher mean perceived effectiveness score (M = 28.50) among the 20 second-year science students, compared to dark chocolate (M = 20.55) The higher mean score for pure black coffee suggests that students experienced greater perceived effectiveness when consuming pure black coffee compared to dark chocolate.

The standard deviation suggests moderate variability in students' perceptions, with scores ranging from 17.00 to 36.00, (SD=5.357) showing that while most students found coffee effective, the level of perceived effectiveness differed among individuals. While the small standard deviation (SD = 1.791) indicates consistent student responses, with perceived effectiveness scores ranging from 16.00 to 24.00, suggesting that dark chocolate produced a more uniform but lower stimulant effect among students.

Table 9. Descriptive Statistics for perceived effectiveness

	Per-Effect (CO)	Per-Effect (CH)
Valid	20	20
Missing	20	20
Mean	28.20	20.55
Std. deviation	5.357	1.791
Minimum	17.00	16.00
Maximum	36.00	24.00

3.5. Focus and Concentration (Objective 2)

The level of focus and concentration of second-year science students was evaluated when using pure black coffee and dark chocolate. The analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between the two stimulants, $t(19) = -7.016, p < .001$.

Table 10. Paired Samples T-Test for focus and concentration

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p
COFFEE	CHOCOLATE	-7.016	19	< .001

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Pure black coffee obtained a mean focus and concentration score of (M= 32.85) with a standard deviation of (SD=5.314), indicating a moderate level of perceived focus enhancement with noticeable variation in students' experiences. Whereas, dark chocolate recorded a higher mean focus and concentration score of (M=40.85) with a smaller standard deviation of (SD = 2.961), suggesting stronger and more consistent effects on students' focus and concentration during study sessions.

The finding suggests that students who experienced Dark Chocolate helped them maintain mental alertness and sustain focus and concentration for longer periods during study sessions.

Table 11. Descriptive Statistics for focus and concentration.

	Focus (CO)	Focus (CH)
Valid	20	20
Missing	20	20
Mean	32.85	40.85
Std. deviation	5.314	2.961
Minimum	21.00	36.00
Maximum	42.00	47.00

3.6. Assessing the significant differences between Pure black coffee and Dark Chocolate as stimulants (Objective 3)

Lastly, to assess the significant differences between pure black coffee and dark chocolate as stimulants among second-year science students, a statistical analysis was conducted. The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the two, $t(19) = -5.284, p < .001$.

Table 12. Paired Samples T-Test for significant differences

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p
COFFEE	CHOCOLATE	-5.284	19	< .001

Findings results in pure black coffee having a mean perceived effectiveness of (M = 31.60) with a standard deviation of (SD = 5.548). Scores ranged from 24.00 to 45.00, showing moderate variability in students' perceptions of its effectiveness compared to dark chocolate obtained a higher mean perceived effectiveness of (M=38.20) with a smaller standard deviation of (SD = 3.548). Scores ranged from 30.00 to 47.00, indicating that students generally perceived it as a consistently more effective stimulant.

This indicates that students considered dark chocolate a superior stimulant compared to coffee.

Table 13. Descriptive Statistics for significant differences

	Diff (CO)	Diff (CH)
Valid	20	20
Missing	20	20
Mean	31.60	38.20
Std. deviation	5.548	3.548
Minimum	24.00	30.00
Maximum	45.00	47.00

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3.7. Summary of Findings

Upon synthesizing these findings, it is evident that different stimulants have distinct effects on students' study behaviors and perceived academic performance. The results from the survey, involving 40 participants, indicate that coffee is widely perceived as the more effective stimulant for improving academic preparation. In contrast, dark chocolate appears to be more effective in improving focus and concentration during study sessions.

Moreover, the study revealed that, overall, dark chocolate may be considered a stronger stimulant in terms of cognitive engagement compared to coffee. The data were carefully analyzed and integrated to provide comprehensive insights into the perceived effectiveness of these caffeinated products in supporting students' preparation for examination.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, this study assessed the significant differences between Pure Black Coffee and Dark Chocolate as stimulants among CVSU-CCAT Second Year Science Education students during exam preparation. In terms of alertness, Pure Black Coffee had a higher mean perceived effectiveness ($M=28.50$, $SD=5.357$, scores 17-36) compared to Dark Chocolate ($M=20.55$, $SD=1.791$, scores 16-24), with moderate variability for coffee and more consistent responses for chocolate. Regarding focus and concentration, Pure Black Coffee obtained a mean score of ($M=32.85$, $SD = 5.314$, scores 21-42), while Dark Chocolate recorded a higher mean of ($M=40.85$, $SD = 2.96$, scores 36-47). The paired t-test revealed a statistically significant difference between the two stimulants ($t(19) = -7.016$, $p < .001$), indicating that students perceived Dark Chocolate as significantly more effective in maintaining focus and concentration during study sessions. In terms of overall perceived effectiveness, Pure Black Coffee had a mean of ($M=31.60$, $SD = 5.548$, scores 24-45), whereas Dark Chocolate had a higher mean of ($M=38.20$, $SD = 3.548$, scores 30-47). The paired t-test showed a statistically significant difference ($t(19) = -5.284$, $p < .001$), demonstrating that Dark Chocolate was generally considered a superior stimulant compared to Pure Black Coffee.

Overall, the findings indicate that significant differences exist between Pure Black Coffee and Dark Chocolate in alertness, focus, and overall cognitive performance, with Dark Chocolate generally perceived as more effective during exam preparation.

Based on the result of findings of this study, the following recommendations are presented:

1. For Students:

Students are encouraged to choose stimulants based on their individual needs during examination preparation. Dark chocolate may be considered for sustained focus and longer review sessions due to its balanced cognitive effects, while pure black coffee may be used for short-term alertness. Moderation is advised to avoid possible negative effects such as restlessness or fatigue. Also students are encouraged to practice effective time management and develop consistent study routines to enhance their preparation for examinations. Proper scheduling of review sessions, adequate rest, and balanced nutrition should be prioritized alongside the responsible use of stimulants such as pure black coffee or dark chocolate. By combining healthy study habits with appropriate stimulant use, students may improve focus, reduce exam-related stress, and achieve better academic performance.

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2. For Academic Institutions and Educators:

Educators may consider providing guidance on healthy study habits, including responsible stimulant consumption. Informational discussions or seminars may help students understand how different stimulants affect concentration and mental performance during examinations.

3. For Future Researchers:

Future studies may expand the sample size and include respondents from different academic programs or year levels to increase the generalizability of the findings. Researchers may also explore additional stimulants, measure actual academic performance outcomes, or examine the long-term effects of stimulant consumption on learning and health. In addition, future research may investigate alternative and effective ways of preparing for examinations, such as improved study strategies, and other academic practices that may help students achieve higher examination scores.

4. For Health Awareness:

Students should be made aware of the importance of balanced nutrition, proper sleep, and time management alongside stimulant use. Stimulants should serve as supplementary aids rather than substitutes for healthy study practices.

Conflict of Interest Statement. *The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper. The research was conducted independently and did not receive any funding or support that could influence the outcomes or interpretations presented herein.*

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